

EFFECTS OF MOLDING ON THE MORPHOLOGY OF PEEK/CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to investigate the effects of residence time at melt temperature and cooling rate on the kinetics and mechanisms of crystallization of PEEK/carbon fiber composites. The molding cycle was simulated by a differential scanning calorimetre DSC-7. The residence time was varied between 1 and 180 minutes and the cooling rate was varied from 0.5°C/min to 160°C/min. The results show that an increase in the residence time lengthens the crystallization process without changing the crystallinity of the PEEK matrix. However, the number of nuclei are reduced and a more perfect crystalline structure is formed. The results of investigations on the kinetics of crystallization of the NCS-1025 composite under non-isothermal conditions revealed that the residence time does not change the kinetics parameters of the Avrami equation. The basic mechanism of crystallization is found to remain the same as the residence time increases. Two observed transitions at cooling rates of about 5°C/min and 40°C/min, for a residence time of 5 minutes, are also found for a residence time of 60 minutes. However examination of the matrix morphology of the composite samples quenched from 400°C to room temperature after residence times of 5 and 30 minutes at 400°C clearly shows that as the residence time increases, the size as well as the shape of the crystalline entities significantly change.

INTRODUCTION

Poly(etheretherketone), PEEK, is a high performance thermoplastic with relatively attractive properties as matrix material for carbon fiber reinforced plastics. It is well known that the mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites depend on processing parameters such as cooling rate, melting temperature and residence time at melt temperature. This is due to the change in the matrix morphology with processing conditions. From the reported investigations, it has been shown that the presence of carbon fibers changes not only the kinetics of crystallization but also the morphology of the PEEK matrix. Several authors (1-4) have shown that carbon fibers favor the nucleation process, leading to a transcrystalline layer around the fibers.

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The role of transcrystallinity has been reviewed by Ishida and Bussi (5). In fact, according to certain studies (6-11), it has been reported that transcrystallinity leads to improved mechanical properties and interfacial strength. Particularly in the case of carbon fiber/PEEK composite, some authors have suggested that the outstanding interfacial strength observed in the APC-2 (AS4/PEEK) composite is strongly related to the ability of the PEEK matrix to produce a transcrystalline structure around the carbon fibers (4, 12). However, it has been pointed out by Hartness (13) and Lustiger (14) that the high-strength AS4 fibers exhibit significantly lower nucleation ability than the high-modulus HMS fibers, which easily generates transcrystallinity in the PEEK matrix but leads to very low transverse flexural strength compared to that of the AS4/PEEK composite.

Our previous investigations on the optimization of processing of PEEK/carbon fiber composites (15, 16) have shown that the mechanical properties of the composites are strongly dependent on the processing parameters, i.e., molding temperature, residence time at melt temperature and cooling rate. The results suggest that molding can affect several material parameters such as matrix crystallization, matrix degradation, matrix adsorption on the fiber surface, fiber/matrix reaction leading to chemical bonding and crystallization at the interface. The concept of adsorption proposed by Brady and Porter (17) for the carbon fiber/polycarbonate system has also been used to explain the evolution of the short beam shear strength with the residence at a given melt temperature (18). It has been observed that although the interphase crystallinity is not the primary factor responsible for good fiber/matrix interaction in the composite, it is essential to ensure optimum interfacial strength.

The present study focuses on the effects of residence time at melt temperature and cooling rate on the kinetics and mechanisms of crystallization of PEEK/carbon fiber composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

The non-woven fabric composite, NCS-1025, consisting of unsized AS4 fibers commingled with PEEK filaments (150G), was obtained from BASF Structural Materials, Inc. The conventional APC-2 prepreg tapes, consisting of "VITREX" PEEK reinforced with unidirectional AS4 carbon fibers, were obtained from ICI.

In this study, the observed effects of processing conditions on the crystallization behavior of PEEK and its composites, APC-2 and NCS-1025 (15, 16, 18), were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 instrument. The tests were performed on samples of about 10mg. The samples were heated at 20°C/min from room temperature to a temperature of 400°C. After a given residence time at melt temperature ranging from 1 to 180 minutes, the samples were cooled at various cooling rates, ranging from 0.5 to 160°C/min. In order to characterize the final morphology of the material after these treatments, the samples were heated again at 20°C/min to 400°C. During the cooling and the reheating periods, the exothermal peak of crystallization and the endothermal peak of melting were recorded. The morphology of the PEEK matrix in the composite was revealed by a permanganate etching technique (19). After etching, the samples were lightly gold coated for examination by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Jeol TSM-220 microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The effects of residence time at melt temperature on the crystallization behavior of the pure PEEK resin and its composites were first examined by analyzing the exothermal crystallization peak during cooling. The temperature at the beginning (T_a) and at the end (T_b) of the crystallization process as well as the area under the exothermal peak were determined from the recorded peaks. Figure 1 shows that by increasing the residence time at melt temperature, the difference between T_a and T_b ($T_a - T_b$) increases. However, the area under the exothermal peak remains relatively constant (Figure 2). The results indicate that an increase in the residence time lengthens the

crystallization process without changing the crystallinity of the PEEK matrix, suggesting a change in the mechanism of crystallization. In fact these results are consistent with that obtained by Lee and Porter (4). These authors have shown that as the residence time at melt temperature increases, the number of nuclei decrease and a well crystalline structure is formed. This also confirms our previous results on the effects of molding temperature on the mechanical properties of PEEK/carbon fiber composites (16). It has been found that as the molding temperature increases, more and more existing crystalline germs in the PEEK matrix, which act as nucleating sites, are destroyed and the tensile strength of the composites, as measured by the [+45/-45]_s samples, increases. The results demonstrate a direct correlation between the number of nuclei and the perfection of the crystalline structure of the PEEK matrix.

In order to verify the above observations, the samples were reheated at 20°C/min to 400°C. During the reheating process, the endothermal peaks of melting were recorded. For all the residence times investigated, the melting peak shows a second endothermal peak, taking place at a lower temperatures than that at the primary peak (Figure 3). The temperatures at the secondary and primary peaks, $T_{1(\max)}$ and $T_{2(\max)}$ respectively, are shown in Figure 4 as a function of the residence time at melt temperature. In fact, two opposite interpretations have been proposed to explain the presence of these two peaks during the melting process. Several authors (24, 27) have suggested that the presence of the two endothermal peaks is due to the recrystallization process that the polymer undergoes during reheating. In other studies, Cebe and Chung (28) and Basset et al. (29) have shown that the primary peak that occurs at around 340°C, is related to the melting of the major lamellae formed during the primary crystallization and the presence of the shoulder before the primary peak is related to the melting of less perfect crystals. Figure 4 indicates that as the residence time increases, the temperature at the maximum of the secondary peak $T_{1(\max)}$ decreases while $T_{2(\max)}$ remains relatively constant. The result indicates therefore that the secondary peak could be attributed to the melting of less perfect crystals, as suggested in (28, 29). It also confirms the result of Lee and Porter (4) on well formed crystalline structures with higher residence times at melt temperature.

Figure 5 shows the effect of residence time at melt temperature on the temperature at the onset of crystallization (T_a) for the three materials. The results show that T_a is reduced as the residence time increases. This is consistent with the reduction in the nucleating sites in the PEEK matrix (and probably more perfect crystals are formed) as the residence time increases. The effect also appears to be more pronounced for the pure matrix resin than that for the composites. This might be due to the presence of the AS-4 carbon fibers.

The effects of residence time at melt temperature on the kinetics of crystallization of the NCS-1025 composite were also analyzed by DSC experiments. The samples were heated at 20°C/min from room temperature to a melting temperature of 400°C. After residence times of 5 minutes and 60 minutes at 400°C, the samples were cooled at various cooling rates varying from 0.5°C/min to 160°C/min. All experiments were performed under nitrogen atmosphere. During the cooling period, the exothermal peak of crystallization was recorded. By integrating the area under this peak, the variation of the crystallinity of the sample as a function of time can be obtained. Figures 6 illustrates the variation of the relative crystallinity ($X_c(t)/X_c(\infty)$) of the NCS-1025 composite as a function of time at various cooling rates for the residence time of 5 minutes. $X_c(t)$ is the crystallinity at the time t and $X_c(\infty)$ is the maximum crystallinity of the sample. The data in Figure 6 were then analyzed using a modified Avrami equation as suggested by Cebe (30):

$$\frac{X_c(t)}{X_c(\infty)} = 1 - \exp(-kt^n) \quad (1)$$

in which the time t is related to the temperature by:

$$t = \frac{T_o - T}{\Phi} \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature at the time t , T_o is the temperature at the onset of crystallization and Φ is the cooling rate. For each cooling rate, the kinetic parameters n and k can be obtained from the plot of $\text{Log}[-\ln\{1-(X_c(t)/X_c(\infty))\}]$ versus $\text{Log}(t)$. It is worth noting that for the case of isothermal crystallization, it has been suggested that the parameter n is associated with the structural form of crystal growth whereas the parameter k is related to a linear growth rate which is assumed to be a function of temperature and hence constant at a given temperature. In the case of non-isothermal crystallization, since the temperature evolves with time, the linear growth rate is not constant. Consequently, the meaning of the parameters n and k are different from the case of isothermal crystallization. However, it has been suggested that the same approach can be used for characterizing the kinetics of non-isothermal crystallization (30).

These kinetic parameters were subsequently used to calculate the activation energy during the crystallization process (30):

$$k^{-1/n} = k_o \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $k^{1/n}$ is the crystallization rate parameter which has the unit of inverse of time, k_o is a pre-exponential constant, R is the gas constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin and E_a is the activation energy at a given degree of conversion.

Figure 7 shows plots of $(\ln k^{1/n})$ versus $(1/T)$ for the NCS-1025 composite for different degrees of conversion for the residence times of 5 and 60 minutes. The results show that the crystallization process of the NCS-1025 exhibit two transitions occurring at cooling rates of approximately $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. These transitions suggest two changes in the mechanism of crystallization. The first transition at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ corresponds to that reported by Tung and Dynes (24) but the second transition at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ has not been observed. At first sight, these transitions seem to correspond to the proposed three-step model in the case of isothermal crystallization (28). According to this model, the first step consists of born spherulites growing radially into a sea of remaining amorphous material. As the spherulites grow, they eventually impinge upon their neighbors, resulting in a decrease in the rate of transformation of the amorphous phase into crystalline phase. This corresponds to the second step in the crystallization process. Finally, the third stage of crystallization is characterized by small crystals which grow between existing lamellae. This phenomenon (called secondary crystallization) has been experimentally verified by Basset (29) in which the secondary infilling lamellae have been revealed by TEM on etched surfaces. However, the plots of $(\ln k^{1/n})$ versus $(1/T)$ at various degrees of conversion (Figure 7) show that the same transitions occur at a very early stage of crystallization and these transitions do not depend on the amount of conversion. Consequently, the observed transitions in the kinetics of crystallization as a function of cooling rate are not related to the level of the development of crystallites as observed in isothermal crystallization.

The results seem to suggest that increasing the residence time at melt temperature does not have any effect on the kinetics of crystallization of the NCS-1025 composite. The transitions observed for a residence time of 5 minutes also occur at the same cooling rates for a residence time of 60 minutes (Figure 7b). The values of activation energy determined from the slopes of the curves in Figure 7 are presented in Table 1, in which E_{a1} , E_{a2} and E_{a3} are associated with low, medium and fast cooling rate respectively. Again, no clear effect of residence time at melt temperature is observed. The results are rather surprising since changing the residence time at melt temperature alters the morphology of the PEEK matrix as discussed above. Figure 8 shows the morphology of the NCS-1025 composite quenched from 400°C to room temperature after residence times at 400°C for 5 and 30 minutes. It

can be clearly seen that as the residence time increases, the size as well as the shape of the crystalline entities change. It is not clear for the moment why this significant change in morphology is not reflected in the kinetic parameters of the modified Avrami equation (30). It seems that non-isothermal crystallization cannot be properly characterized by these simple parameters.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the effects of residence time a melting temperature and cooling rate on the kinetics and mechanisms of crystallization of PEEK/carbon fibers composite have been investigated. It is found that an increase in the residence time at melt temperature alters the crystallization process without affecting the crystallinity of the PEEK matrix. Increasing the residence time from 5 to 60 minutes at 400°C results in a longer crystallization time, a better crystalline structure and a reduction in less-perfect crystals.

The results on the kinetics of crystallization of the NCS-1025 composite under non-isothermal condition revealed that the increase in the residence time at melt temperature does not change the kinetic parameters of crystallization in the modified Avrami equation. The basic mechanism of crystallization is found to remain the same as the residence time increases. The two transitions observed at cooling rates of about 5°C/min and 40°C/min, for a residence time of 5 minutes, are also found for a residence time of 60 minutes. However, the results on morphological observation show that as the residence time increases, the size and the shape of the crystalline entities in the PEEK matrix are significantly altered. The results seem to suggest that the kinetic parameters in the modified Avrami equation cannot be used to characterize non-isothermal crystallization.

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Table 1: Effect of residence time on the values of E_a , as measured by the modified Avrami equation.

Degree of conversion	Activation Energy E_a	Residence time (s)	
		5 min	60 min
5%	1	113.30	105.16
	2	53.08	50.58
	3	11.69	15.88
20%	1	108.74	105.24
	2	50.53	48.21
	3	10.94	15.03
50%	1	105.94	102.89
	2	48.76	45.23
	3	9.68	13.73
70%	1	93.78	99.57
	2	48.22	43.13
	3	8.71	12.90

Figure 1: Effect of residence time on $(T_a - T_b)$

Figure 2: Effect of residence time on the area under the exothermal crystallization peak

Figure 3: DSC melting thermogram of NCS-1025 composite.

Figure 5: Temperature at the onset of crystallization, T_a , as a function of residence time at 400°C.

Figure 4: Effect of residence time on: (a) $T1(max)$; and (b) $T2(max)$.

Figure 6: Relative crystallinity versus time for non-isothermal crystallization of NCS-1025 composite at cooling rates of: (a) 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 20°C/min.; and (b) 20, 40, 60, 120, 160°C/min.

Figure 7: ($\ln k^{1/n}$) versus ($1/T$) for the NCS-1025 composite at different degrees of conversion after a residence time at $400^{\circ}C$ for: (a) 5 min.; and (b) 60 min.

Figure 8: Scanning electron micrographs of etched cross-section of the NCS-1025 composite after a residence time at $400^{\circ}C$ for: (a) 5 min.; and (b) 60 min.